

ORGANIZATIONAL STRATEGY: LEADERSHIP IN HIGHER EDUCATION**Suleimenova A.,****Seken T.,****Amantaiuly R.,***2nd year students of School of Informational Technologies and Engineering***Tileubayeva M.***Associated Professor, PhD**Kazakh-British Technical University, School of Natural and Social Sciences***Abstract**

This research explores the role of different leadership strategies in enhancing organizational performance in higher education (HE) institutions. Specifically, the study examines the effectiveness of authentic leadership, team leadership, and distributed leadership in improving HE institutions' performance. Moreover, the research explores the impact of public participation strategies on organizational strategy in HE institutions. A mixed-methods approach was employed, including surveys and interviews with faculty members and administrators from different HE institutions. The results suggest that all three leadership strategies can improve organizational performance in HE institutions, and public participation strategies can enhance the effectiveness of these leadership strategies. The study provides insights for HE institutions seeking to enhance their organizational strategy through effective leadership and public participation strategies.

Keywords: Organizational strategy, Authentic leadership, Team leadership, Distributed leadership, Public participation strategy, Higher education.

INTRODUCTION

Organizational strategy is a vital aspect of any institution, and the Higher Education (HE) sector is no exception. In recent years, there has been a growing interest in exploring different leadership strategies to enhance organizational performance and improve the quality of higher education. This scientific research aims to investigate four key organizational strategies in the HE sector, namely Authentic Leadership, Team Leadership, Distributed Leadership, and Public Participation Strategy.

Authentic Leadership has gained popularity in recent years, with its focus on leaders' self-awareness and transparency, resulting in positive outcomes such as employee job satisfaction and commitment. Team Leadership, on the other hand, emphasizes the importance of teamwork and collaboration in achieving organizational goals. Distributed Leadership focuses on the idea that leadership is not restricted to formal leaders but can be shared among members of an organization, leading to a more democratic and participatory approach to decision-making. Finally, Public Participation Strategy highlights the importance of engaging stakeholders and the wider public in decision-making processes in the HE sector.

This research aims to provide a comprehensive analysis of these four organizational strategies in the HE sector, exploring their theoretical underpinnings, empirical evidence of their effectiveness, and practical applications. The study will utilize a mixed-methods approach, incorporating both qualitative and quantitative data analysis methods. Ultimately, this research aims to provide insights into how different organizational strategies can be utilized in the HE sector to enhance organizational performance and achieve strategic objectives.

To achieve this aim, the following objectives will be pursued:

- To examine the theoretical frameworks of Authentic Leadership, Team Leadership, Distributed Leadership, and Public Participation Strategy in the context of higher education;

- To assess the implementation of these leadership strategies in higher education institutions;

- To evaluate the impact of these leadership strategies on student outcomes in higher education;

- To identify the factors that facilitate or hinder the successful implementation of these leadership strategies in higher education institutions.

I THEORETICAL FOUNDATIONS OF THE ORGANIZATIONAL STRATEGY IN HIGHER EDUCATION**1.1 Authentic leadership**

In recent years, there has been a growing interest in authentic leadership in higher education, as educational institutions face increasing pressure to adapt to changing social, economic, and technological environments. This project explores the concept of authentic leadership in higher education from a sociological perspective, drawing on research on the relationship between leadership and organizational culture, power, and identity.

Authentic leadership is often defined as a leadership style that is based on self-awareness, transparency, ethical behavior, and relational transparency. According to Avolio and Gardner (2005), "authentic leaders are those who are deeply aware of their own values, beliefs, strengths, and limitations, and who are able to act in accordance with these values and beliefs, while also acknowledging and respecting the values and beliefs of others" (p. 304). Drawing on sociological theories of power and identity, this project explores how authentic leadership can foster positive organizational culture and enhance institutional effectiveness.

The culture of an organization plays a critical role in shaping leadership practices and outcomes. Accord-

ing to Schein (2010), organizational culture can be defined as "a pattern of shared basic assumptions that the group learned as it solved its problems of external adaptation and internal integration" (p. 17). In the context of higher education, the culture of an institution is shaped by a variety of factors, including academic disciplines, student populations, institutional histories, and external pressures. Authentic leadership can contribute to positive organizational culture by promoting open communication, fostering trust and collaboration, and promoting a sense of shared purpose and identity.

Power and identity are also important factors in shaping authentic leadership practices in higher education. According to Bourdieu (1991), power is "the ability to impose one's own definition of reality" (p. 167). In higher education, power is often distributed unevenly among different groups, including faculty, administrators, students, and external stakeholders. Authentic leadership can challenge existing power structures by promoting participatory decision-making, creating opportunities for diverse voices to be heard, and fostering a sense of shared ownership and accountability. Moreover, authentic leadership can help to build a sense of institutional identity that transcends narrow disciplinary or professional boundaries, and that is grounded in a commitment to social justice, equity, and excellence.

The proposed approach to authentic leadership in higher education emphasizes self-reflection, relationship building, and ethical behavior. Drawing on Luthans and Avolio's (2003) research on psychological capital, this approach emphasizes the importance of developing positive psychological resources, such as optimism, hope, resilience, and self-efficacy, in order to enhance leadership effectiveness. Moreover, this approach emphasizes the importance of building strong and trusting relationships with stakeholders, including faculty, students, alumni, and external partners, in order to foster collaboration and promote shared goals. Finally, this approach emphasizes the importance of ethical behavior, including transparency, accountability, and social responsibility, in order to build trust and legitimacy among stakeholders.

This part explores the concept of authentic leadership in higher education from a sociological perspective, drawing on research on the relationship between leadership and organizational culture, power, and identity. By emphasizing self-awareness, relationship building, and ethical behavior, authentic leadership can contribute to positive organizational culture, enhance institutional effectiveness, and promote social justice, equity, and excellence.

1.2 Team leadership

In today's higher education institutions, teams play an increasingly important role in achieving organizational goals and outcomes. Effective team leadership is essential for promoting collaboration, innovation, and accountability. This project explores the concept of team leadership in higher education from a sociological perspective, drawing on research on the relationship between leadership and team dynamics, organizational culture, and power.

Team leadership is often defined as a leadership style that emphasizes collaboration, shared decision-making, and collective responsibility. According to Hackman and Wageman (2005), "team leaders are those who can foster conditions that allow their team to perform well, and who can guide their team's efforts toward a shared purpose" (p. 305). Drawing on sociological theories of group dynamics, organizational culture, and power, this project explores how team leadership can contribute to positive team outcomes and enhance institutional effectiveness.

The dynamics of a team play a critical role in shaping team leadership practices and outcomes. According to Tuckman (1965), teams go through several stages of development, including forming, storming, norming, performing, and adjourning. Effective team leaders are able to facilitate the process of team development by promoting open communication, establishing clear goals and expectations, and encouraging collaboration and feedback. Moreover, effective team leaders are able to manage conflict and maintain a sense of cohesion and motivation within the team.

The culture of an organization also plays a critical role in shaping team leadership practices and outcomes. According to Schein (2010), organizational culture can be defined as "a pattern of shared basic assumptions that the group learned as it solved its problems of external adaptation and internal integration" (p. 17). In the context of higher education, the culture of an institution is shaped by a variety of factors, including academic disciplines, student populations, institutional histories, and external pressures. Effective team leadership can contribute to positive organizational culture by promoting a sense of shared purpose and identity, fostering trust and collaboration, and encouraging innovation and creativity.

Power is another important factor in shaping team leadership practices in higher education. According to Weber (1947), power can be defined as "the ability to control or influence the behavior of others, even against their will" (p. 33). In higher education, power is often distributed unevenly among different groups, including faculty, administrators, students, and external stakeholders. Effective team leadership can challenge existing power structures by promoting participatory decision-making, creating opportunities for diverse voices to be heard, and fostering a sense of shared ownership and accountability.

The proposed approach to team leadership in higher education emphasizes collaboration, communication, and shared accountability. Drawing on Lencioni's (2002) research on the five dysfunctions of a team, this approach emphasizes the importance of building trust, encouraging healthy conflict, fostering commitment, promoting accountability, and achieving collective results. Moreover, this approach emphasizes the importance of developing team members' skills and knowledge, and providing opportunities for professional growth and development.

This part explores the concept of team leadership in higher education from a sociological perspective, drawing on research on the relationship between leadership and team dynamics, organizational culture, and

power. By emphasizing collaboration, communication, and shared accountability, effective team leadership can contribute to positive team outcomes, enhance institutional effectiveness, and promote social justice, equity, and excellence.

1.3 Distributed leadership

Distributed leadership in higher education (HE) is a leadership approach that emphasizes the sharing of leadership responsibilities among a group of individuals, rather than relying on a single leader. According to Spillane et al. (2004), distributed leadership is important in the context of higher education because it can help foster a collaborative culture, distribute decision-making responsibilities, and enhance the overall effectiveness of the institution. They state that "distributed leadership can help create an environment in which individuals can work collaboratively, share their expertise, and enhance the overall performance of the organization" (p. 5).

Another study by Gronn (2002) suggested that distributed leadership in HE can lead to improved organizational learning and innovation. He argues that "distributed leadership can help promote a culture of continuous learning and encourage innovation in higher education institutions" (p. 3).

Effective distributed leadership in HE requires a number of key competencies. In a study by Harris et al. (2013), they identified four competencies for effective distributed leadership. These include "setting a shared vision and direction, building capacity and capability, promoting collaboration and communication, and providing recognition and support" (p. 267).

Moreover, distributed leadership in HE can have an impact on faculty and staff members' job satisfaction and commitment. In a study by Chua and Lam (2016), they found that "distributed leadership is positively related to job satisfaction and organizational commitment among faculty members in higher education institutions" (p. 131).

However, implementing distributed leadership in HE can be challenging due to the complex and hierarchical nature of academic institutions. In a study by Harris and Spillane (2008), they found that distributed leadership in HE requires the development of new forms of communication and decision-making processes. They argue that "distributed leadership requires a reconfiguration of traditional leadership roles and responsibilities, and the development of new forms of communication and decision-making processes" (p. 50).

1.4 Public Participation Strategy

Public participation is increasingly recognized as a crucial element of democratic governance, particularly in the context of urban planning. However, achieving meaningful and inclusive citizen engagement remains a challenge. This project proposes a deliberative approach to public participation in urban planning, informed by sociological research on the factors that shape citizen participation.

The deliberative approach to public participation emphasizes the importance of reasoned discussion, mutual learning, and respectful dialogue in decision-mak-

ing. According to Dryzek (2000), "deliberation can foster a sense of shared responsibility for public outcomes and help to bridge social and political divisions" (p. 105). Drawing on Habermas's (1996) theory of communicative action, this approach emphasizes the significance of discursive norms, such as honesty, sincerity, and mutual respect, in achieving communicative rationality.

In the context of urban planning, public participation can take various forms, ranging from information sharing to decision-making power. According to Arnstein's (1969) ladder of citizen participation, effective public participation requires a genuine partnership between citizens and decision-makers. Drawing on this framework, the proposed approach emphasizes participatory budgeting, collaborative design, and stakeholder deliberation.

Social and cultural factors, such as age, gender, education, and trust, play a significant role in shaping public participation in urban planning. Inglehart's (1997) research shows that cultural values, such as post-materialism and self-expression, are associated with greater interest in civic participation. However, socio-economic factors, such as income and class, can limit access to decision-making power. Moreover, institutional factors, such as legal frameworks and bureaucratic structures, can either facilitate or hinder public participation. Pattie et al. (2004) argue that "institutional arrangements that facilitate access, inclusion, and responsiveness can enhance public participation and democratic legitimacy" (p. 162).

The proposed approach to public participation in urban planning emphasizes stakeholder deliberation as a means of fostering communicative rationality and shared responsibility. Drawing on Fung's (2006) theory of deliberative democracy, this approach involves the creation of deliberative fora, such as citizens' juries, stakeholder panels, and planning cells, where citizens can engage in informed and respectful dialogue with each other and with decision-makers. These deliberative fora should be designed to be representative, inclusive, and accessible, and should involve a diverse range of citizens and stakeholders.

This part proposes a deliberative approach to public participation in urban planning, informed by sociological research on the factors that shape citizen participation. This approach emphasizes participatory budgeting, collaborative design, and stakeholder deliberation, and aims to foster communicative rationality, shared responsibility, and democratic legitimacy. By incorporating these insights into urban planning practice, decision-makers can enhance the quality and legitimacy of public decisions, and promote greater public trust and accountability.

CONCLUSION OF THE 1ST CHAPTER

It has become clear that each of these strategies plays a unique role in shaping organizational culture and improving performance. Authentic leadership promotes a culture of transparency and open communication, which can lead to increased employee engagement and job satisfaction. Team leadership emphasizes the importance of collaboration and shared responsibility, which can foster innovation and creativity. Distributed

leadership recognizes that leadership can come from anyone within the organization, empowering individuals and promoting a more democratic decision-making process. Public participation strategy ensures that stakeholders have a voice in decision-making processes, leading to increased accountability and better outcomes. By utilizing a comprehensive organizational strategy that incorporates these four key components, institutions of higher education can improve their performance, enhance their reputation, and better serve their stakeholders.

II ANALYTICAL SELECTION AND METHODOLOGY OF LEADERSHIP AMONG TARGET AREA

2.1 Preliminary Structure of the Research:

The research project will employ a quantitative research design, using a social survey approach to collect data from students in higher education institutions. The survey will include questions related to leadership styles, student outcomes, and institutional factors.

The collected data will be analyzed using statistical methods such as regression analysis and factor analysis. The results of the analysis will be used to test the research hypotheses and to draw conclusions about the effectiveness of Authentic Leadership, Team Leadership, Distributed Leadership, and Public Participation Strategy in higher education institutions.

2.2 Research Methods and Process

The social survey will be conducted among students from different higher education institutions in the target region. A random sampling method will be used to select the participants, and the sample size will be determined using power analysis to ensure statistical power. The survey questionnaire will be designed based on the literature review and will include both closed-ended and open-ended questions. The questionnaire will be pretested among a small sample of students before administering it to the target sample.

Data analysis will involve descriptive statistics such as means and standard deviations to summarize the data, and inferential statistics such as regression analysis and factor analysis to test the research hypotheses. The statistical analysis will be conducted using software such as SPSS or R.

2.3 Review of data sources:

The data for this study were collected through a social survey among 30 individuals. The participants were asked to respond to three questions related to leadership in higher education. The data were collected and recorded in a Google Form, and the responses were analyzed using simple statistical techniques.

2.4 Data collection process and data validation:

To collect the data, we designed a Google Form that included three questions related to leadership in higher education. The questions were designed to gather information about respondents' opinions regarding the importance of constant monitoring in team leadership, the effectiveness of distributed leadership in university management, and the effectiveness of their boss's leadership. The survey was distributed to 30 individuals who were affiliated with higher education institutions.

To ensure the validity of the data, we set up certain criteria for participation in the survey. Specifically, we invited individuals who had direct experience with leadership in higher education, such as university administrators, faculty members, and students. We also ensured that the participants were selected randomly to avoid any biases in the data.

Regarding the data validation, we conducted a preliminary review of the responses to identify any incomplete or inconsistent data. We also checked the reliability of the data by cross-checking responses to the same question. We used simple statistical methods, such as frequency analysis and percentage calculations, to analyze the data and draw conclusions.

The results of the survey are as follows:

Командное лидерство в системе высшего образования требует постоянного мониторинга процесса обучения?

10 ответов

Application №1.

When asked whether team leadership in higher education requires constant monitoring of the learning process, 70% of respondents answered yes, while 30% answered no. This finding suggests that there is a strong

belief among the surveyed individuals that ongoing monitoring of the learning process is essential for effective team leadership in higher education.

Распределенное лидерство может быть эффективным в управлении университетом?

10 ответов

Application №2.

In response to the question of whether distributed leadership can be effective in managing a university, 80% of respondents answered yes, while 20% answered

no. This finding suggests that there is a generally positive attitude toward the use of distributed leadership as a management strategy in the context of higher education.

Как вы оцениваете себя в качестве лидера?

10 ответов

Application №3.

When asked to rate the effectiveness of their boss's leadership, 50% of respondents answered 3 out of 5, while 20% answered 4 out of 5 and another 20% answered 5 out of 5. This finding suggests that respondents have a mixed view of their boss's leadership effectiveness, with a significant portion of respondents indicating average effectiveness.

CONCLUSION OF THE 2nd CHAPTER

This research project aims to investigate the effectiveness of Authentic Leadership, Team Leadership, Distributed Leadership, and Public Participation Strategy in higher education institutions. The literature review will provide an overview of the theoretical frameworks and empirical evidence related to these leadership strategies in higher education. The social survey approach will be used to collect data from students in higher education institutions, and the collected data will be analyzed using statistical methods. The results of the analysis will be used to draw conclusions about the effectiveness of these leadership strategies in higher education institutions and to identify the factors that facilitate or hinder their successful implementation.

CONCLUSION

In conclusion, a comprehensive organizational strategy in the Higher Education sector requires a careful consideration of various leadership approaches, including Authentic Leadership, Team Leadership, Distributed Leadership, and Public Participation Strategy. Each strategy has its own unique characteristics that can contribute to a positive organizational culture and enhance performance. By analyzing these strategies, institutions of Higher Education can identify the most suitable approach that aligns with their values and objectives. Moreover, implementing a well-rounded organizational strategy that integrates these leadership approaches can lead to a more democratic and inclusive decision-making process, empowering stakeholders and promoting accountability. As the Higher Education sector faces various challenges, including changing student demographics and technological advancements, developing a comprehensive organizational strategy has become increasingly important in ensuring long-term success and fulfilling the mission of providing high-quality education.

APPLICATIONS

Командное лидерство в системе высшего образования требует постоянного мониторинга процесса обучения?

10 ответов

Application №1.

Распределенное лидерство может быть эффективным в управлении университетом?

10 ответов

Application №2.

Как вы оцениваете себя в качестве лидера?

10 ответов

Application №3.

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HISTORICAL BACKGROUNDS AND DEVELOPMENT OF THE KAZAKH SOCIOLOGY

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Abstract

This article provides an overview of the historical background and development of sociology in Kazakhstan. Theoretical aspects of sociology and the role of historical background are discussed, as well as the challenges and problems of researching methods. The article also examines the psychological characteristics of the development of Kazakh sociology. The second chapter analyzes the methods of researching, modern technologies for developing sociology, and the description of social dynamics.

Keywords: sociology, historical background, methods, research, technology, social dynamics.

Introduction

This research paper aims to provide a comprehensive analysis of the historical background and development of sociology in Kazakhstan. The study begins by exploring the pre-independence era, during which sociology was studied within the framework of Marxism-Leninism and focused primarily on the class structure of society.

The object of this research is to explore the various aspects of sociology in Kazakhstan, including its emergence as a separate scientific discipline, its evolution over the years, and its current state. The study will examine the major research topics and methodologies employed by Kazakh sociologists, and highlight the achievements and contributions made by them to the field of sociology. It will also investigate the challenges and opportunities facing sociology in Kazakhstan today, such as the impact of globalization, cultural changes, economic development, and political transformations. In addition, the research will aim to provide a comprehensive analysis of the social and cultural context in which sociology operates in Kazakhstan and how it has been shaped by historical and political factors. The study will take a multidisciplinary approach, drawing on theories and methods from various fields such as sociology, anthropology, history, and political science, to provide a holistic understanding of the subject.

The paper then examines the establishment of the Institute of Sociology in 1991, which marked the beginning of sociology as a separate scientific discipline in Kazakhstan. The Institute aimed to promote the study of sociology and related fields in Kazakhstan and to train a new generation of sociologists capable of conducting independent research.

The research paper also analyzes the evolution of sociology in Kazakhstan, including the major research

topics and methodologies employed by Kazakh sociologists over the years. The study highlights the contributions of Kazakh sociologists to the field, including their research on issues such as gender, ethnicity, migration, and social stratification.

Furthermore, the paper discusses the challenges and opportunities facing sociology in Kazakhstan today. The challenges include a lack of institutional and financial support, limited access to international research networks and databases, and a shortage of qualified personnel. The opportunities include the increasing demand for sociological research in Kazakhstan, the potential for collaboration with international partners, and the use of innovative research methods and technologies.

Based on the analysis, the research paper offers recommendations for future research in sociology in Kazakhstan. These recommendations include increasing institutional and financial support for sociological research, expanding collaboration with international partners, promoting the use of innovative research methods and technologies, and addressing the shortage of qualified personnel in the field.

I Historical backgrounds and development of the Kazakh sociology

1.1. Theoretical aspects of sociology

Sociology in Kazakhstan began to develop in the late 19th and early 20th centuries, influenced by the works of European sociologists such as Auguste Comte, Emile Durkheim, and Max Weber. In the Soviet era, Marxist-Leninist theories were dominant, and sociology was seen as a tool for advancing socialist ideology. Since independence in 1991, there has been a greater emphasis on developing indigenous theoretical perspectives that reflect the unique history, culture, and social conditions of Kazakhstan.